

An efficient 3D color optical microscopic imaging system through high precision biological focal stacking

Ziqian Hong

Basis International School Park Lane Harbour

Ziqian.hong15375-biph@basischina.com

Abstract

Optical microscopic imaging is an effective tool for biological research. However, limitations in traditional microscopy present difficulties in colored 3D imaging. Also, the shallow depth of field of the microscope cannot generate an all-in-focus image, posing a challenge to biological observation. This paper proposes a new precise colored 3D microscopic imaging system to increase the accuracy of biological imaging and taxonomy. The proposed method consists of a high-precision automated focal scanning system (AFS) and an efficient focal stacking algorithm. The AFS is capable of precisely moving a minimum distance of 10 μm along the z-axis. Our focal stacking algorithm identifies the in-focus regions through the Laplacian pyramid to generate colored and depth information. Experimentation shows that the proposed method yields high-resolution colored images and precise depth information. The study provides the foundation for future 3D reconstruction and accurate species identification.

1. Introduction

When observing complex microscopic organisms, due to high magnification rates, microscopes have a shallow depth of field [1, 2]. Therefore, a single image could not capture all the characteristics of microscopic samples. However, to obtain accurate depth information and an in-focus image efficiently is critical for biologists to gain a comprehensive view of a microscopic sample [3]. An accurate and clear image displays the characteristics of a sample that aids tasks such as taxonomy while precise depth information reveals the 3D structures of the sample [4]. Current methods for 3D imaging include Stereo vision, Light sheet fluorescence microscopy, and Confocal microscopy. Stereo vision fuses images from different viewpoints and compares these images to generate a 3D model. Examples of stereo vision include Convolutional neural network [5] and Multi-view information fusion [6]. For regular scenes, stereo vision can generate colored 3D models at low com-

putational costs without sophisticated equipment. Nonetheless, due to the limited depth of field of a microscope, much of an image may appear blurred and unsuitable for stereo vision.

In Light sheet fluorescence microscopy (LSFM), a sheet of laser light within the sample is used to excite its fluorophores, which emits light a detector captures to create a 3D representation of the specimen. Rasmi *et al.* improved LSFM in 2015 by limiting the angular views required for image acquisition [7]. In 2020, Sala *et al.* used LSFM to reconstruct individual cells [8]. LSFM precisely reveals the internal structures of a specimen. However, it requires the use of expensive laser sources and detectors. Additionally, the intensity of the fluorescence contains only gray-scale information.

Confocal microscopy focuses a laser through a pinhole onto a specific point on the specimen, and only light reflected from that specific point is detected to create a 3D model. Jourlin *et al.* applied Confocal microscopy to human hair in 1993. In 2004, Hardie *et al.* used Confocal microscopy to reconstruct the Cochlea [9]. Confocal microscopy yields high precision, Nonetheless, the process of scanning every point on the specimen is time-consuming.

As shown above, current 3D imaging methods often lack color or require sophisticated equipment and significant amounts of time. Also, methods that rely on fluorescence, including LSFM and Confocal microscopy suffer from photo-bleaching, making long-term observations of samples challenging. However, by using focal stacking techniques to extend the depth of field (DOF), a precise depth map and a high-resolution colored image can be efficiently generated with simple image collection equipment. Since the fused image contains information from all focal

Received: 30 November 2023 Accepted: 05 February 2024

Published: 25 March 2024

Citation: Hong, Z. (2024). An efficient 3D color optical microscopic imaging system through high precision biological focal stacking. *The Young Scientist*, 3(1), 41-48.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10935434>

depths, it has better quality than any image in the focal stack [10]. Also, the proposed white-light imaging method avoids the problems caused by fluorescence imaging. This study proposes an efficient colored 3D imaging method that requires only simple equipment. In the proposed method, an automatic focal scanning method (AFS) is used to collect microscopic images from different focal depths. A focal stacking method is then applied to fuse the images and estimate a depth map. The information obtained provides the foundation of a colored 3D model. Compared with other traditional methods, our method demonstrated superiority in smoothness and detail preservation over traditional light microscopic imaging. The proposed process is illustrated in Figure 1.

The main contributions of this paper include (1) a simple AFS for the automated collection of images from different focal depths. (2) A focal stacking algorithm that performs precise depth map estimation and generates an all-in-focus fused image.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces our AFS and 3D reconstruction algorithm. Section 3 displays our experimental results followed by comparisons with other traditional methods. Section 4 discusses the effectiveness of our method. Section 5, our last section, gives the concluding remarks.

2. Methods

2.1. Automated focal scanning method

The AFS equipment we used in this study was a high-precision multimodal layer-scanning optical microscopy imaging platform (DP-401) Figure 2 provided by Daphnia Technology Inc. The AFS utilizes an optical microscope controlled by a stepping motor. The structure is composed of a camera and its objectives suspended from a stand containing the electric motors. The camera is a Sony A7MIII [11]. A7MIII contains a full-frame image sensor with a resolution of 24.2MP and a dynamic range of 14 bits. Below the camera is a set of zoom objectives capable of magnifying the sample by up to 20X. The sample is placed on a dark illumination light source, which can be adjusted to concentrate light from different angles. Finally, the light source is positioned on a mobile platform, which is controlled by an adjuster for motion across the xy-plane. Every time the software sends an electric signal, it triggers the rotation of the built-in screw. The screw's rotation is then translated into the vertical motion of the camera, moving it along the z-axis. During image collection, The computer software sends signals at regular intervals to rotate the screw for a fixed degree and capture images of the sample from different focal depths. Specifically, the camera can precisely move a minimum vertical distance of 10 μm per interval. Since the camera's location is predetermined, a depth map can be generated without estimating the viewpoint for every

image.

2.2. Focal stacking and 3D reconstruction

2.2.1 Image registration

Changing the focal depth results in the sample being shifted or zoomed. Therefore, image registration is necessary. Since images from different focal depths have different out-of-focus regions, it is challenging to find a common in-focus location that can be used for point-based image registration methods. Thus, the Normalized cross correlation image registration method (NCC), proposed by Sarvaiya *et al.*, is applied [12]. While other non-rigid image registration methods such as the Scale invariant feature transform (SIFT) [13] may produce better results, they are computationally expensive. Also, most misalignments under the microscope require only rigid transformations to fix [14]. Hence, template matching is sufficient. In NCC, the annotator first selects a rectangular box that contains the sample on any image within the stack. The rectangular box is set as the template image. NCC computes the cross-correlation values of the template image with all locations on the registered image. Define the template image and the registered image as $A(x, y)$ and $B(x, y)$ respectively. Then, NCC is defined as:

$$NCC(A, B) = \frac{\sum_{i,j} (A(i, j) - \mu_A)(B(i, j) - \mu_B)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i,j} (A(i, j) - \mu_A)^2 \sum_{i,j} (B(i, j) - \mu_B)^2}} \quad (1)$$

such that μ_A and μ_B represent the mean values of images A and B. The NCC ranges from -1 to 1, with a high value indicating a better match. The region with the highest cross-correlation value is then selected. As NCC uses all points in the template image, it is robust to blurred regions and changes in the value of individual pixels. Figure 3 shows the template and the registered image.

2.2.2 Background segmentation

To remove the background for further processing, The Any-labeling segmentation software developed by Nyuyen and Viet Anh is used [15]. Anylabeling uses points hinted by the annotator to append or remove regions until the desired region of interest is selected. Specifically, the region of interest is expressed as a mask, $M_1(x, y)$. When $M_1(i, j) = 0$, the pixel (i, j) is part of the sample whereas $M_1(i, j) = 1$ indicates the pixel is part of the background.

2.2.3 Point selection

The locations that provide stronger indications of depth information have their intensity values for different focal depths sparsely spread out. Therefore, for every location,

Figure 1: The workflow

by computing the standard deviation (STD) of the intensity values along the z-axis, the coordinates containing the most depth information can be determined. The STD array representation $\sigma(x, y)$ is defined as follows:

$$\sigma(x, y) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (D(i, x, y) - \mu_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

where N , $D(z, x, y)$ and μ_z represent the number of samples, the image stack, and the mean value respectively. Using coordinates that contain weak or no indication of depth will result in a misleading depth map. Therefore, The coordinates within the foreground are sorted based on their respective STD values to find the median STD value. Only coordinates with STD values greater than the median will be used to determine depth information. The selected foreground coordinates with sufficiently high STD values will be stored as a mask. The mask $M_2(x, y)$, illustrated in Figure 4 is defined below and :

$$\text{if } \sigma(x, y) > \tilde{\sigma}, M_2(x, y) = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{else, } M_2(x, y) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}$ is the median value of all values in $\sigma(x, y)$ such that $M_1(x, y) = 1$.

2.2.4 Laplacian pyramid

The high-frequency signals represent the most distinctive features within a local region. Subsequently, high-frequency components contain features that can be used to measure depth. To decompose our dataset into different frequency components, the Laplacian pyramid, proposed by Burt and Adelson in 1983, is constructed [16]. To generate the Laplacian pyramid, the Gaussian pyramid, $GP_{z,i}$, is first created by down-sampling and applying the Gaussian Blur for suitable iterations, which is set to 6. The Gaussian blur, $GB(x)$ is defined as:

$$GB(x) = x \cdot \frac{1}{256} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 4 & 6 & 4 & 1 \\ 4 & 16 & 24 & 16 & 4 \\ 6 & 24 & 36 & 24 & 6 \\ 4 & 16 & 24 & 16 & 4 \\ 1 & 4 & 6 & 4 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$GP_{z,1} = D(z) \quad (6)$$

$$GP_{z,i} = GB(\text{pyrDown}(GP_{z,i-1})) \quad (7)$$

where D represents the image stack and pyrDown represents down-sampling by a factor of 2. The difference between successive Gaussian pyramid layers is taken to create

Figure 2: Microscope structure

Figure 3: Up: template image Bottom: registered image

Figure 4: left: Region of interest right: selected mask

the Laplacian pyramid, LP.

$$LP_{z,i} = GP_{z,i-1} - pyrUp(GP_{z,i}) \quad (8)$$

$$LP_{z,6} = GP_{z,6} \quad (9)$$

$pyrUp$ represents up-sampling an image by a factor of 2. The frequency of information decreases for lower pyra-

mid layers. To determine depth information, for every image within the dataset, their respective top, high-frequency pyramid layers are compared. The maximum intensity value across different images is found for every coordinate in the top pyramid layer. Illustrated below is the depth map $DM(x, y)$:

$$DM(i, j) = arg \max_z(LP_{z,1}) \quad (10)$$

$arg \max_z$ represents the index corresponding to the maximum values along the z-axis. Finally, for every coordinate, the focal depth of the image containing the maximum intensity value is set as the location's depth, creating the depth map.

Similarly, the all-in-focus image must contain the strongest information for high-frequency components. The maximum value is again selected across all images, for all pyramid layers except the bottom low-frequency layer. To highlight the high-frequency components, which contain the distinctive features of the sample, the low-frequency signals are weakened. The minimum value across images is selected for the low-frequency, bottom layer. The selected pixel for each layer CP_i is defined as follows:

$$if \ i = 6, \ CP_i = \min_z(LP_{z,i}) \quad (11)$$

$$else, \ CP_i = \max_z(LP_{z,i}) \quad (12)$$

where \max_z and \min_z represent the maximum and minimum pixel values along the z-axis. Figure 5 represents the pyramid layers after point selection. Lastly, the all-in-focus image is reconstructed by combining the previously selected maximum or minimum layer values. Starting from the bottom layer, every layer is up-sampled and added to the previous layer. The ultimate sum is the all-in-focus image, F_1 .

$$F_6 = CP_6 \quad (13)$$

$$F_i = pyrUp(F_{i+1}) + CP_i \quad (14)$$

2.2.5 Depth estimation

For points previously determined as uncertain based on their STD, the values of adjacent pixels are used to estimate their intensities. Specifically, the set K_x consisting of the $x\%$ certain points closest to the uncertain pixel is chosen to estimate the value of the uncertain pixel. x is set to 1 in this experiment. The impact of the adjacent pixels on the uncertain pixel is inversely proportional to the distance between them. The updated $DM(x, y)$ is:

$$if \ not \ (M_1(x, y) \ \& \ M_2(x, y)) : \quad (15)$$

$$DM(x, y) = \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in K_x} DM(i, j) \cdot dist((i, j), (x, y))}{\sum_{(i,j) \in K_x} dist((i, j), (x, y))} \quad (16)$$

Figure 5: Laplacian pyramid layers ordered with decreasing size

where $dist((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2))$ is the distance between (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) .

2.2.6 3D model generation

The 3D model is represented at a colored point cloud. The depth map and all-in-focus image are then concentrated into a rgbxyz point cloud: $R((x, y, z), (r, g, b))$

$$R((x, y, z), (r, g, b)) = [(x, y, DM(x, y)), F_1(x, y)] \quad (17)$$

3. Experiments and results

3.1. Evaluation metrics

Entropy (EN), Standard deviation (STD), and the Natural image quality evaluator (NIQE) are applied to quantitatively assess the results. The entropy of an image is calculated based on the probability distribution of the pixel values [17]. A high entropy shows pixel values being spread out over a wide range, thus including complexity and detail. Entropy is defined as:

$$EN = - \sum_{k=0}^{255} \log(p_k) \quad (18)$$

where p_k represents the number of pixels with intensity k in a gray-scale image. STD reflects the distance of pixel values

from the mean. Similarly, high STD represents scattered pixel values, indicating higher contrast and detail. STD is computed as:

$$STD = \sqrt{\frac{1}{H * W} \sum_{i,j} (I(i, j) - \mu)^2} \quad (19)$$

where W, H represents the width and height of the image and μ is the mean intensity value. NIQE is an image quality assessment model developed by Mittal *et al.* in 2012 [18]. The model predicts the extent of image distortion. A low NIQE indicates an undistorted, natural image. Instead of using human-rated images, NIQE is trained with statistical patterns from natural images. Therefore, NIQE is unexposed to distorted images. A pre-trained NIQE model from PYIQA is utilized to assess whether the images appear natural to the human eye [19].

3.2. Results analysis

Table 1: Image quality assessment.

Method	EN	STD	NIQE
LP_3	5.83	42.84	4.54
LP_4	5.87	44.30	4.52
LP_5	5.94	45.66	4.22
LP_6 (Ours)	5.70	47.08	4.23
LP_7	6.23	46.07	4.49
LP_8	6.54	43.33	4.57
Max	5.60	39.90	6.03
Gradient	5.96	32.70	16.21

Table 2: NIQE comparison for Figure 10.

Index	Ours	Gradient
a	7.19	6.87
b	5.85	6.59
c	5.15	8.35
d	7.37	7.79
e	6.42	7.79
f	5.39	7.81
g	8.66	7.97
h	6.07	6.75

To test our 3D reconstruction algorithm, experiments were performed with images of an ant's compound eye and Gammaridea. The ant's eye dataset consists of 78 images taken with 10X magnification and a step of 15 μm between images. The Gammaridea collection has 30 images, 10X magnification, and 45 μm steps. The proposed method is compared with a gradient-based method developed by Wlodek [20] and the maximum value method. Different numbers of layers for the Laplacian pyramid and different

Figure 6: Laplacian Layer Detail Comparison

Figure 7: Ours and Gradient detail comparison

percentages for K_x are tested. All experiments were performed in a Python 3.9 environment. As shown in Table 1, NIQE is significantly lower in the proposed method compared to the Maximum and Gradient methods.

When collecting images from different focal depths, the transition between background and sample is inevitably blurred for most focal depths. Diffraction during microscopy also made the sample's edges brighter. While the Gradient method creates noise on the edges of samples, the proposed method handles the transition smoothly. As shown in Figure 7, a smoother edge creates a better visual perception. In Figure 6, a closeup of a stripe on the sample is shown. Since the maximum value method is unable to separate different frequency information, it completely failed to capture the high-frequency stripe. This is further reflected by the low STD value for the Maximum value method; low-contrast details are often ignored. On the other hand, the Laplacian pyramid captured the stripe. Figure 6b is marginally clearer than Figure 6a and Figure 6c since there is a higher contrast between the detail and its

Figure 8: Depth map comparison

lighter surroundings. There is also a fogging effect on Figure 6c compared to Figure 6a and Figure 6b. Due to the Gaussian Blur performed during pyramid construction, the reconstructed image is fogged compared to the original image. While a greater number of pyramid layers yields more entropy and detail, it also causes greater fog. After experimentation, six pyramid layers are chosen to be the optimum balancing point between detail and fog. In Figure 8, different K_x and the Gradient method are compared for depth map generation. In the center, low-contrast areas of Figure 8e, the Gradient method produced only noise. In low-contrast regions, there is little to no gradient information available. However, due to our depth estimation algorithm, the depth of low-contrast regions can be estimated using the depths of other points. In Figure 8a and to a lesser extent Figure 8b, artificial transitions between different estimated regions are observed. Without a sufficient number of selected points, the change caused by major relocation in selected points can be abrupt. On the other hand, in Fig-

Figure 9: 3D model of a Gammaridae copepod

ure 8d, while transitions are smooth, variations in depth are small. When an excessive number of points are chosen, depth information from distant, unconnected points is included. This tends to pull the estimated depths for all points to a common average, reducing the depth information preserved. After testing, K_1 is decided to be the lowest K_x such that there are no artificial transitions. The depth map, visualized as a 3D model, is shown in Figure 9. As shown in Figure 10, experiments on other focal stacks are also performed. Displayed in Table 2, most images achieved higher quality than traditional methods.

4. Discussion

From the analysis above, it can be seen that after an optimum selection of pyramid layers and points used for estimation, the proposed method creates smoother transitions and preserves more detail than traditional methods. Not only is the proposed AFS straightforward, but it also enhances the quality of the fused image. Also, due to the predetermined camera viewpoints, the depth map is precise. However, the points below deserve further investigation:

(a) **There is a lack of depth information in low-contrast areas.** Low contrast areas in the interior of samples often contain little depth information. While the proposed depth estimation algorithm made these regions appear smooth and natural, there is still a loss of detail. An algorithm that calculates the depth of low-contrast regions directly should be devised.

Figure 10: Other images of focal stacks

(b) **The Laplacian pyramid creates a blurring effect on the edges.** The Laplacian pyramid does not reconstruct the image perfectly; the successive Gaussian Blurs gave the image a higher contrast than the original image. Suitable post-processing techniques can be applied to decrease contrast.

(c) **The percentage of points selected in Section 2.2.3 may not be optimal.** While the median was chosen to be to divide certain and uncertain points, the actual number of certain points differs for different samples. A larger low-contrast zone may decrease certain points while a longer sample edge may increase the number of points. A threshold determined by specific image conditions may be more optimal.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, a new image collection system and AFS for colored microscopic imaging is presented. Not only is the AFS straightforward, it predetermines the camera's viewpoint so that viewpoint estimation is no longer necessary. Also, the focal stacking method precisely determines the depth map and fused image at low computational costs. Comparisons between our method and other traditional methods are made. It can be seen that the proposed method creates a smoother and clearer result. However, the current method lacks a set of criteria for subjectively assessing image quality. Future work should focus on deep learning. While the acquisition of 3D datasets is challenging, deep learning methods are more adaptable to different conditions.

References

- [1] Lingbo Jin et al. "Deep learning extended depth-of-field microscope for fast and slide-free histology". In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117.52 (2020), pp. 33051–33060.
- [2] Yuchen Qiu et al. "Impact of the optical depth of field on cytogenetic image quality". In: *Journal of Biomedical Optics* 17.9 (2012), pp. 096017–096017.
- [3] Samuel J Yang et al. "Assessing microscope image focus quality with deep learning". In: *BMC bioinformatics* 19 (2018), pp. 1–9.
- [4] Renaud Boistel et al. "The future of three-dimensional microscopic imaging in marine biology". In: *Marine Ecology* 32.4 (2011), pp. 438–452.
- [5] Chenhao Lin and Ajay Kumar. "Contactless and partial 3D fingerprint recognition using multi-view deep representation". In: *Pattern Recognition* 83 (2018), pp. 314–327.
- [6] Chaoqun Hong et al. "Multi-view ensemble manifold regularization for 3D object recognition". In: *Information sciences* 320 (2015), pp. 395–405.
- [7] CK Rasmi et al. "Limited-view light sheet fluorescence microscopy for three-dimensional volume imaging". In: *Applied Physics Letters* 107.26 (2015).
- [8] Federico Sala et al. "High-throughput 3D imaging of single cells with light-sheet fluorescence microscopy on chip". In: *Biomedical optics express* 11.8 (2020), pp. 4397–4407.
- [9] Natalie A Hardie, Glen MacDonald, and Edwin W Rubel. "A new method for imaging and 3D reconstruction of mammalian cochlea by fluorescent confocal microscopy". In: *Brain research* 1000.1-2 (2004), pp. 200–210.
- [10] Ren C Luo, Chih-Chen Yih, and Kuo Lan Su. "Multisensor fusion and integration: approaches, applications, and future research directions". In: *IEEE Sensors journal* 2.2 (2002), pp. 107–119.
- [11] *Sony Alpha 7 III Specifications*. Accessed: December 22, 2023. URL: <https://electronics.sony.com/imaging/interchangeable-lens-cameras/full-frame/p/ilce7m3-b>.
- [12] Jignesh N Sarvaiya, Suprava Patnaik, and Salman Bombaywala. "Image registration by template matching using normalized cross-correlation". In: *2009 international conference on advances in computing, control, and telecommunication technologies*. IEEE, 2009, pp. 819–822.
- [13] David G Lowe. "Object recognition from local scale-invariant features". In: *Proceedings of the seventh IEEE international conference on computer vision*. Vol. 2. Ieee, 1999, pp. 1150–1157.
- [14] Andrew Shacklock and Wenting Sun. "Integrating microscope and perspective views". In: *Proceedings of the 2005 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 2005, pp. 454–459.
- [15] Viet Anh Nguyen. *AnyLabeling - Effortless data labeling with AI support*. URL: <https://github.com/vietanhdev/anylabeling>.
- [16] Peter J Burt and Edward H Adelson. "The Laplacian pyramid as a compact image code". In: *Readings in computer vision*. Elsevier, 1987, pp. 671–679.
- [17] Du-Yih Tsai, Yongbum Lee, and Eri Matsuyama. "Information entropy measure for evaluation of image quality". In: *Journal of digital imaging* 21 (2008), pp. 338–347.
- [18] Anish Mittal, Rajiv Soundararajan, and Alan C Bovik. "Making a "completely blind" image quality analyzer". In: *IEEE Signal processing letters* 20.3 (2012), pp. 209–212.
- [19] Chaofeng Chen and Jiadi Mo. *IQA-PyTorch: PyTorch Toolbox for Image Quality Assessment*. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/chaofengc/IQA-PyTorch>. 2022.
- [20] J Wlodek, KJ Gofron, and YQ Cai. "Achieving 3D imaging through focus stacking". In: *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2054. 1. AIP Publishing, 2019.